

Abstract:

The present study entitled "An Economic Analysis on Marketing of Milk in Gopalganj District of Bihar". It was founded that there are three marketing channels involved in marketing of milk in Gopalganj district of Bihar; (Channel 1 – Producer- Consumer), (Channel 2- Producer-Milkman-Consumer) and Channel 3 (Producer – Milk Cooperative- Milk Man – Consumer) The majorly preferred marketing channel by respondents in the study area is Channel 3. In channel 1, total marketing cost is Rs. 5, total marketing margin is Rs. 5, marketing efficiency of channel 1 is 4% and price spread in channel 1 is Rs. 5, and in channel 2, total marketing cost is Rs. 5, total marketing margin is Rs. 15, marketing efficiency of channel 2 is 2.5% and price spread in channel 2 is Rs 10 and in channel 3, total marketing cost is Rs. 16, total marketing margin is Rs 24, marketing efficiency of channel 3 is 1.62% and price spread in channel 3 is Rs. 23.

Keyword: Marketing Efficiency, Marketing Margin, Marketing Cost and Price Spread.

Introduction

Milk is a nutrient-rich liquid sustenance produced by animals' mammary glands. It is the principal source of nourishment for young animals (including breastfed human newborns) before they can digest solid food. Colostrum, or early-lactation milk, contains antibodies that improve the immune system, lowering the risk of several illnesses. Milk includes a variety of nutrients, including protein and lactose. While humans are the principal users of other mammals' milk, additional interspecies milk drinking has been reported.

In 2019, around 730 million tonnes of dairy milk were obtained from farm animals. India is the world's largest milk producer and exporter of skimmed milk powder, but due to rising demand, it may become a net importer. The top three milk exporters are New Zealand, Germany, and the Netherlands. China and Russia were the world's major importers until 2016, when they were able to produce enough to fulfil their own demand, resulting in an excess of milk on the global market. More than six billion people worldwide consume milk and milk products, and between 750 and 900 million people live in dairy-farming households. Plant milks are increasingly consumed as plant-based alternatives to dairy milk.

Research Methodology:**Table 1: Selection of Respondents:**

District	Block	Villages	Respondents			
			Small	Medium	Large	Total
Gopalganj	Phulwariya	Bairagi Tola	10	3	3	16
		Balbhadar Parsa	7	7	2	16
		Bansi Batraha	8	3	5	16
		Dubaulia	7	5	4	16
		Gidha	10	3	3	16
TOTAL		5	42	21	17	80

Analytical Tools**Mean**

$$m = \frac{\text{sum of the terms}}{\text{number of terms}}$$

Marketing Efficiency

$$\text{Marketing Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Net price received by producer's} - \text{Consumer price}}{\text{Total marketing cost}}$$

Marketing Cost:

$$\text{Marketing Cost (MC)} = \frac{\Delta TC}{\Delta Q}$$

Price Spread:

Consumer price paid price - Net price received by producer

Marketing Margin Marketing Margin = Producer price – Raw

Table 3: Marketing cost, Marketing margin, Marketing Efficiency and Price Spread in marketing of milk in the existing marketing channels.

Channel 1 - Producer-Consumer

Selection of the District:

There are 38 District and 9 division in Bihar state. Out of these Gopalganj district of Bihar was selected for the present study on the basis of maximum area under Cattle rearing and milk production.

Selection of Block:

The district consists of 14 blocks. Phulwariya was purposefully chosen from among these. The temperature and soil conditions on the block are ideal for cattle raising. This block's farmer has been raising cattle for numerous years.

Selection of Villages: The block development office reported 106 villages in Phulwariya. Out of 106 villages in Phulwariya Block, 5% were chosen as having a good level of cow husbandry and milk production.

Selection of Respondents:

From the selected village, list of all the cattle rearing farmer was obtained from the block development office in each selected village. Ascending order on the basis of size of cattle rearing capacity for the selection of cultivators from families was listed and 10% farmers from all the selected village were randomly selected and then the selected farmers were classified into three sizes of groups

material

Results And Discussion

Table 2: Marketing Channel Preference of respondents in marketing of milk.

Sr. No.	Channels	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Channel 1	10	12.5
2	Channel 2	20	25
3	Channel 3	50	62.5

Table 2 demonstrates that respondents favour three channels for milk marketing. Channel 1 is favoured by 10 respondents (12.5%), channel 2 is liked by 20 respondents (25%), and channel 3 is preferred by 50 respondents (62.5%).

Channel 2- Producer-Milkman- Consumer

Channel 3: Producer – Milk Cooperative- Milk Man – Consumer

Sr. No.	Particulars	Channel 1	Channel 2	Channel 3
		Value in Rs/Liter	Value in Rs/Liter	Value in Rs/Liter
1	Selling price of producer	35	40	47
	Transportation cost and others	5		5
	Margin of producer	5	10	17
	Net price received by producer	30	40	42
Cost incurred by milk cooperatives		--	--	
A	Collection charges	--	--	5
B	Miscellaneous charges	--	--	2
Total Marketing cost incurred by milk cooperative		--	--	7
Margin of Milk-cooperatives		--	--	3
Selling price of Milk cooperatives to milkman		--	--	57
Cost incurred by milk man		--		
a	Transportation and other costs incurred	--	5	4
Margin of milkman		--	5	4
	Selling price to consumer	40	50	65
•	Total market margin	5	15	24
•	Total marketing cost	5	5	16
•	Marketing efficiency	4%	2.5%	1.62%
•	Price Spread	5	10	23

Table 3 reveals that the marketing costs for milk are incurred by different channels, with the producer selling milk to consumers at Rs 40, the milkman selling milk to milkmen at Rs 40, and the milkman marketing milk at Rs 50. The marketing price for milk from producer to milk cooperative is Rs 47/liter, and the margin of producer in selling milk from producer to cooperative is Rs 17/liter. The selling price for milk from milk cooperative to milkman is Rs 57/liter, with a profit margin of Rs 3 per liter. The cost incurred by milk cooperative in marketing milk to milkman is Rs 7. The selling price of milk from milkman to consumer is Rs 65, with a profit margin of Rs 4 and marketing cost incurred by milkman in marketing milk is Rs 4. The total marketing cost for channels 1 is Rs 5, channel 2 is Rs 15, and channel 3 is Rs 24. The marketing efficiency for channels 1 is 4%, channel 2 is 2.5%, and channel 3 is 1.62%. The price spread in channels 1 is Rs 5, channel 2 is 10, and channel 3 is 23.

Conclusion:

Milk supply chains are crucial for controlling milk quality and supply fluctuations, which are unique to the sector. Supply chain management is essential for gaining a competitive advantage in the business world due to increased competition, high service expectations, and competitive pricing. The Indian dairy industry must focus on overcoming challenges and overcoming issues. Global milk demand is growing by 15 million tons per year, primarily in developing countries. Small-scale dairy farmers can produce this volume, creating 3 million jobs per year. This presents an opportunity to build a sustainable dairy chain that sources milk from smallholder farmers to meet local and global market demands. To capitalize on this opportunity, a sound dairy development strategy should be based on the principle of 'creating value' in every segment of the dairy chain. This means that every player in the chain, including farmers, farm input suppliers, milk traders, MILK MAN, and retailers, should make a profit, resulting in higher returns than costs. A well-functioning dairy chain also benefits consumers by allowing them to obtain more dairy products for the same amount of money or spend less for the products they consume.

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